

RestPoll

Communication & management plan

WP7: COORDINATING, NETWORKING, AND DATA MANAGEMENT

TASK 7.2: DATA MANAGEMENT AND PUBLICATION STRATEGY

Deliverable 7.1

31 March 2025
Version 4- Public

Dimitry Wintermantel, Amibeth Thompson, Felix Fornoff, Julia Osterman,
Alexandra Klein
University of Freiburg
Anda Adamsone-Fiskovica
Baltic Studies Centre
Maj Rundlöf
Lund University

RestPoll

**Restoring Pollinator habitats across European agricultural
landscapes based on multi-actor participatory approaches**

Prepared under contract from the European Commission

Grant agreement No. 101082102

EU Horizon Europe Framework Programme

Project acronym: **RestPoll**
 Project full title: **Restoring Pollinator habitats across European agricultural landscapes based on multi-actor participatory approaches**
 Start of the project: Oct 2023
 Duration: 48 months
 Project coordinator: Professor Alexandra-Maria Klein
 University of Freiburg, Freiburg, Germany
 www.restpoll.eu

Deliverable title: Communication & management plan
 Deliverable n°: D7.1
 Nature of the deliverable: Report
 Dissemination level: Public

WP responsible: WP7
 Lead beneficiary: University of Freiburg (ALU)

Citation: Wintermantel, D., Thompson, A., Fornoff, F., Osterman, J., Adamsone-Fiskovica, A., Rundlöf, M. & Klein, A.M. (2024). *Communication & management plan, Version 4*. Deliverable D7.1 EU Horizon RestPoll Project, Grant agreement No. 101082102.

Due date of deliverable: Month 3
 Actual submission date: Month 3

Deliverable status:

Version	Status	Date	Author(s)
1.0	Submitted Document	22 December 2023	Dimitry Wintermantel, Felix Fornoff, & Amibeth Thompson, Alexandra-Maria Klein <i>University of Freiburg</i>
1.1	Revisions/F eedback	31 December 2023	Anda Adamsone-Fiskovica, <i>Baltic Studies Centre</i> / Julia Osterman, <i>University of Freiburg</i> / Maj Rundlöf, <i>Lund University</i>
2.0	Revised Document	5 April 2024	Amibeth Thompson <i>University of Freiburg</i>
3.0	Revised Document	15 October 2024	Amibeth Thompson <i>University of Freiburg</i>

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

4.0	Revised Document	31 March 2025	Amibeth Thompson, <i>University of Freiburg</i> / Anda Adamsone-Fiskovica, <i>Baltic Studies Centre</i>
-----	------------------	---------------	--

****This is a public version of the Deliverable. Email addresses of members and links to internal documents have been removed. ****

The content of this deliverable does not necessarily reflect the official opinions of the European Commission or other institutions of the European Union.

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

Table of Content

Summary.....	5
Project coordinator & manager.....	5
1. General principles.....	5
2. Multi-level coordination structure.....	5
Project management team.....	5
Work Package (WP) leaders.....	6
RestPoll Members.....	6
3. Internal communication.....	6
3.1. Communication channels.....	6
3.2. Platforms with Project information.....	8
3.3. Communication expectations.....	9
Communication with Stakeholders.....	9
4. Reporting.....	10
3. 1. Milestones and Deliverables reporting.....	10
3.2. Risk reporting.....	10
3.3. Visibility of EU Flag and Funding Statement.....	11
3.4. Gender equality and diversity Statement.....	11
5. Authorship Policy.....	12
5.1. Criteria for authorship.....	12
5.2. Primary authorship.....	12
5.3. Senior authorship.....	12
5.4. Sequence of remaining authors.....	12
5.5. Authorship statements.....	12
5.6. Authorship acknowledgements.....	12
5.7. Data authorship.....	13
5.8. Determining potential authors.....	13
6. Data management workflow.....	14
7. Open Science Policy.....	15
7.1. Open Access requirements.....	15
8. Additional open science guidelines.....	17
9. Version 2.....	17
10. Version 3.....	17
11. Version 4.....	17
12. Appendices.....	17
10.1. Appendix 1.....	17
10.2. Appendix 2.....	19

Summary

The purpose of the Communication & management plan is to identify the channels of internal communication, the reporting requirements, and the code of conduct (i.e. authorship policy, data management workflow, and open science policy) that will help the management and success of the RestPoll project.

PROJECT COORDINATOR & MANAGER

Project Coordinator: Alexandra-Maria Klein

Project Manager: Amibeth Thompson

1. General principles

Every partner must ensure that good research and communication practices are followed in line with the grant agreement (particularly article 14 and Annex 5) and the key principles of reliability, honesty, respect and accountability.

2. Multi-level coordination structure

The communication structure within the RestPoll project is multi-levelled (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Multi-level coordination structure within RestPoll.

PROJECT MANAGEMENT TEAM

The project management team (project coordinator and manager) coordinates the information and workflow across the Work Packages (WP). They will inform WP leaders of upcoming deliverables and milestone deadlines and will conduct quarterly status updates in the form of a short meeting.

The project management team will also communicate with RestPoll members to inform them of upcoming events and deadlines, the project's progress, completed achievements (Deliverables and Milestones), and updates to project policies. Monthly project information updates will be sent with completed milestones, deliverables or tasks and a preview of what to expect in the next three months.

WORK PACKAGE (WP) LEADERS

It is the WP leader's responsibility to inform RestPoll members of relevant developments and research flow within the WP. Depending on WP-specific needs and considerations, WPs will have meetings of various regularity (see Section 3) to update members involved in the progress and status of the different tasks and to allow space for discussion, questions, and collaborations across tasks within and between the WPs.

List of Work package leaders

Work Package	Leader name
WP1	Alexandra Klein
WP2	Maj Rundlöf
WP3	Nicola Gallai
WP4	Martin Hvarregaard Thorsøe
WP5	Lynn Dicks
WP6	Elise de Groot
WP7	Alexandra Klein

RESTPOLL MEMBERS

It is RestPoll Members' responsibility to report to the project management team communication and dissemination activities that are conducted within the project.

These activities can be added to this database:

RestPoll_Dissemination&Communication_List.xlsx

Please provide email addresses of new and leaving member via an email to Amibeth. New members will be sent RestRoll Welcome Guide. They will also be asked to fill out a form and for a photo to be used for the RestPoll website. Members who have left the project will be removed from the members list, but will be archived.

3. Internal communication**3.1. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS****Overview of Communication Channels**

Topic	Primary Channel	Audience	Frequency
General Announcements	Email (restpoll@nature.uni-freiburg.de)	All Members	As Needed
Project Information + Progress	Email (restpoll@nature.uni-freiburg.de)	All Members	Monthly
Work Package Information + Progress	WP Email Lists	WP members	As Needed
Urgent Issues	Slack / WhatsApp	Relevant Leads or Members	Immediate
Project Updates + Progress	Quarterly Meetings	WP leads	Quarterly
Asking Questions or Reporting Issues	Slack / WhatsApp	Relevant Leads or Members	As Needed

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

1. Email

Email lists have been created for 1) all members of the RestPoll project and 2) for each work package. The general email list will be used for internal communication of the project (i.e. announcement of meetings, information, etc.) relevant for all members. With discretion, this list can be used to forward relevant information, such as job announcements, relevant projects, meetings or conferences, to all members. This email should only be used if the announcements are of interest to the overall project consortium. Additionally, replies to emails to this address should in general not be “replied to all”, to avoid that all partners receive too many emails. It is recommended to reply to individual persons and to think carefully when to reply to the overall consortium. For example, congratulations for a published deliverable does not need to reach the overall consortium.

Work package email lists have been created for communication with involved members of the WPs and tasks. These lists will be used to communicate WP specific emails. All members are free to join any of the lists.

List of Work Package Email Lists

WP1	Establishing and testing co-adaptive management in a European restoration network	[Removed for public version]
WP2	Demonstrating context dependency, scalability, and synergies across pollinator restoration measures at the landscape scale and beyond	[Removed for public version]
WP3	Assessing socio-economic co-benefits, barriers, and incentives for pollinator restoration	[Removed for public version]
WP4	Enabling conditions for long-term pollinator restoration and Living Labs	[Removed for public version]
WP5	Integrating assessment tools for decision, education, and evaluation	[Removed for public version]
WP6	Communicating and exchanging knowledge and engagement	[Removed for public version]

To sign-up for the different lists, please send a blank email to the email addresses below. You will then receive a confirmation email. Please follow those instructions (i.e. replying to the email). Afterwards, you should receive a welcome email.

WP1	[Removed for public version]
WP2	[Removed for public version]
WP3	[Removed for public version]
WP4	[Removed for public version]
WP5	[Removed for public version]
WP6	[Removed for public version]

2. WhatsApp

A WhatsApp community was created for immediate communication of questions or issues and brief updates of tasks progress. A channel was created for field work and for the Living Lab. Announcements to all members can also be made within the community.

After you have joined, we ask that you please add your information to this database, so we can keep track of members information:

RestPoll_LLS_WhatsApp_Group_Contact_Info.xlsx

Information and decisions discussed exclusively within the WhatsApp community will be disseminated as a digest to the rest of the consortium via email.

3. Slack

This platform will be used for internal communication outside of email. Slack allows you to send personal or group messages to team members, video chat, and also has different channels, where you can post information, links, documents, or ask questions. All members can join Slack.

4. Video Conference Meetings

Online video conference meetings will be used within and among Work Package groups to exchange ideas. Zoom and Microsoft Teams, or similar program will be used, based on the organizing institution. Meetings will not be held outside of working days (i.e. holiday and weekends) and hours and will respect the differences in time-zones among the partners. When scheduling a meeting, the specified time zone should be included in the invitation to avoid confusion with members outside of the planned times zone.

Work packages host regular meetings for members to stay up-to-date on the progress of the WP and tasks, along with reporting any issues or ask for input. The frequency of the meetings varies within the WPs.

Frequency of Work Package Meetings

Work Package	Frequency
WP1	Twice a year- before fieldwork & after fieldwork
WP2	Monthly- last Friday morning of the month
WP3	As necessary
WP4	Bimonthly- Feb-Apr-June-Aug-October
WP5	Quarterly- end of month of each quarter
WP6	As necessary
WP7	As necessary

3.2. PLATFORMS WITH PROJECT INFORMATION

Members Area RestPoll website

This will be the central point for partners to find various communication tools, templates, guidelines, and other documents (such as presentations, reports, posters, and deliverables in general). Information regarding the access and use of the members area

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

will be sent to project members later. To sign up, go to www.restpoll.eu and click on the “Visit member area” in the right-hand corner and register as a member.

Joint RestPoll Drive

A cloud storage platform was created to be used by partners to store and share data. More detailed information for data management and storage can be found in the Data Management Plan (D7.2). For access to the RestPoll drive, please send an email to Amibeth.

Trello

This platform will be used by partners to get an understanding of how the tasks, work packages, etc. have been divided. Partners can see important information and which goals and To Do's each group has. All members can join the Trello board.

3.3. COMMUNICATION EXPECTATIONS

The Grant Agreement stipulates the need for ongoing monitoring and reporting of work package advancement, assessed in relation to deliverable and milestone schedules. Additionally, it underscores the importance of vigilant risk management to ensure timely and budget-compliant project completion. Work Package (WP) leaders should promptly identify and report any emerging risks or issues, to facilitate their review.

The purpose of this real-time tracking is to identify bottlenecks, risks, issues, or delays as they arise to develop and deploy contingency plans in a timely manner.

The project manager, together with the coordinator, will inform the project members of new information or changes in a timely manner. The project manager will provide reminders and status report updates on a periodic basis to each task leader. It is also the responsibility of each task leader and member to inform the project manager and/or coordinator of any new progress, risks, or outputs in a timely manner.

Project-related activities, e-mail correspondence, organisation of online and face-to-face meetings are to be avoided outside working days and hours, respecting the differences in time-zones and national holidays applicable to countries represented by the consortium.

COMMUNICATION WITH STAKEHOLDERS

Consortium members that wish to communicate with stakeholders at Living Lab (LL) and Case Study Areas (CSA) should contact the responsible RestPoll representative (see Table 1).

Table 1: Contact information for RestPoll representatives for the different Case study areas (CSA) / Living labs (LL) in the project.

CSA / LL	Partner	Country	RestPoll contact
ALU	ALU	Germany	Felix Fornoff, Nick Rosenberger
TUM	TUM	Germany	Paula Prucker
CER	CER & BNPI	Hungary	Sándor Piross

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

CCI	CREAF- CERCA & IRTA- CERCA	Spain	Laura Roquer-Beni
CON	CONFAGRI	Italy	Elisa Tomassi
BSC	BSC	Latvia	Anda Adamsone-Fiskovica
EIA	ENSEFA, IAMM, INRAE, ADASEA32	France	Aurlie Belveze, Georgios Kleftodimos, Annie Ouin, Nicola Gallai
KEN	UREAD, AVALON, Innocent	UK	Michael Garratt
SOM	UCAM, BBCT	UK	Jacqui James, Richard Comont, Lynn Dicks
MON	AU	Denmark	Claus Rasmussen, Martin Hvarregaard Thorse
UFZ	UFZ	Germany	Oliver Schweiger, Christophe Dominik
WBF	WBF	Switzerland	Louis Sutter
UTI	UTH, IAMM	Greece	George Vlontzos, Georgios Kleftodimos
CYF	CYFNU YFNU	Ukraine	Mariia Fedoriak
NBT	NBDC, TCD	Ireland	Jane Stout, Sarah Larragy
WUN	WU	Netherlands	David Kleijn, Remco Ploeg
ULU	ULUND	Sweden	Maj Rundlf

4. Reporting

3.1. MILESTONES AND DELIVERABLES REPORTING

Deliverables and milestones must be delivered using the RestPoll milestones and deliverables templates (available on the RestPoll website's members area [www.restpoll.eu], Appendix 1). A reminder will be sent to the associated task lead and co-lead(s) **three** and **two months** before the deadline by the project manager. The documents must be sent to the project coordinator and manager at the latest by the **1st of the month** it is due (advisably by the 15th of the month before). After they have provided feedback, task lead(s) and co-leads, in correspondence with their specific working partners, shall timely implement changes and send them back to the project coordinator and manager for publication on the RestPoll Website and EU Portal.

Partners are obliged to properly implement the actions and tasks they have been assigned to in the grant agreement, even if they are not explicitly related to a specific milestone or deliverable. The status and progress of each task will be reported during the Annual Group Meetings (AGMs). If partners are at risk of failing to perform a task, reach a milestone, or produce a deliverable, they should communicate this openly to the Task/WP lead, project coordinator, and manager.

3.2. RISK REPORTING

Risk management will be assessed periodically (every 3-6 months) using the Work Package Status Report Template (available on the RestPoll Drive), which will be sent to the responsible lead by the project manager. It is requested that any foreseeable or

potential risks be reported to the respective Task/WP leads, project coordinator, and manager as soon as possible. Risks can include but are not limited to: change/loss of key staff, extreme weather conditions during field work, lack of available data or inability to access data, insufficient participation, inability to implement measures within case study areas or establish case study areas and living labs, low response rates, etc.

When a Beneficiary or Work Package leader identifies a risk during or outside of the WP Status Report, they should report it to the project manager. The project coordinator and project officer will timely review the risks and advise as required.

Critical risks and risk management strategies have already been identified in the Grant Agreement (pg. 105). If new risks arise, mitigation measures will be identified and implemented. Financial risk will be assessed and reported with the financial risk mitigation process form (available on the RestPoll website's members area [www.restpoll.eu], Appendix 2).

3.3. VISIBILITY OF EU FLAG AND FUNDING STATEMENT

In agreement with the Grant Agreement (Article 17.2), communication activities related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate). This is available for download on the European Union website (https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en).

Funded by the
European Union

Likewise, any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

3.4. GENDER EQUALITY AND DIVERSITY STATEMENT

All milestones and deliverables must include a dedicated section on gender equality and diversity initiatives, highlighting achievements, challenges, and proposed actions for improvement. All reports and activities must follow the guidelines outlined in the Gender equality and diversity plan (M25).

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

5. Authorship Policy

5.1. CRITERIA FOR AUTHORSHIP

Authors should have contributed meaningfully to at least one or all of the following to ensure that an intellectual input is provided:

- Study design (including significant development or co-development of key ideas);
- Data collection and/or curation (beyond what would be expected of a paid technical assistant, implying active and thoughtful participation in planning and execution);
- Data analysis;
- Data interpretation;
- Manuscript writing.

Any author (irrespective of whether they have left the position held at the time of contribution) should be given the opportunity to actively contribute to the writing, critical review and revision of the final output. This includes the revision of manuscripts that are to be resubmitted for publication.

5.2. PRIMARY AUTHORSHIP

The primary authorship is assigned to the person who has contributed most significantly to the study/deliverable. Typically, first authorship is granted to the person that has written the first draft of the manuscript and/or analysed the data. In cases where several participants have equally shared this leading role, joint first authorship can be acknowledged, in accordance with the guidelines set by the respective academic journals/books.

5.3. SENIOR AUTHORSHIP

Final placement in the author list is typically reserved for the person who has overseen and is chiefly accountable for the entirety of the study and has been the driving intellectual force behind the work (unless they also lead the writing, in which case they assume primary authorship). In cases where several individuals share significant supervisory or oversight responsibilities, the manuscript can reflect this through the acknowledgement of co-senior authors, in line with the guidelines of the respective journals/books.

5.4. SEQUENCE OF REMAINING AUTHORS

The order in which the names of authors other than the primary and senior authors should be determined by the primary and senior authors in agreement with the co-authors. Primary and senior authors may choose to involve their co-authors in rating the relative contributions of each co-author (systematically) to decide on authorship position. When several co-authors contributed similarly, an alphabetic order by surname is recommended.

5.5. AUTHORSHIP STATEMENTS

All publications should clearly state the contributions of each author to aspects like study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, and the writing of the manuscript (following the standards set by the relevant academic journals/books).

5.6. AUTHORSHIP ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

Authors acknowledge important work and contributions of those that do not meet the criteria for authorship, including workers and funders who have enabled the research. If the coordinator and project manager are not co-authors, we encourage you to thank them for setting up the project and for coordination of the LLs and case-study areas. Also, authorship **acknowledgements must include**: “This study was conducted using funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project number 101082102 (RestPoll “Restoring pollinator habitats across European agricultural landscapes based on multi-actor participatory approaches”)” or on manuscripts not directly funded by RestPoll but you receive funding from RestPoll, please include the following statement, “[Your Name/Initials] was funded by the project RestPoll “Restoring pollinator habitats across European agricultural landscapes based on multi-actor participatory approaches” within European Union’s Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082101.”

5.7. DATA AUTHORSHIP

Authorship of databases generated within RestPoll should be assessed and determined following the process described above.

5.8. DETERMINING POTENTIAL AUTHORS

1. Initial selection and re-assessment. At the start of any publication within RestPoll, a broad discussion should take place to identify who the likely authors are. These should subsequently be given the opportunity to contribute. If they do so meaningfully (as outlined above), they should be granted authorship. Work package or Task leaders are urged to be inclusive and to involve as broad and diverse a group of contributors as is feasible. The project coordinator (alexandra.klein@nature.uni-freiburg.de) and project manager (amibeth.thompson@nature.uni-freiburg.de) must be kept in the loop about new internal subprojects via email. They have the right to forward these ideas to the consortium or relevant WPs/people to broaden the group of contributors. Collaboration in elaborating joint publications beyond work packages is highly encouraged, and people willing to contribute to publications stemming from work packages that they are not formally associated with should indicate to the task leaders how they would like to contribute. Likewise, task leaders should not hesitate to contact people outside their work package directly to call for contributions to emerging publications or other activities such as additional funding applications to support or extend RestPoll.

2. Abstract circulation. At least **four weeks before submitting a manuscript to a journal/book, the manuscript’s title, abstract, and proposed list of authors** must be emailed to all RestPoll members (restpoll@nature.uni-freiburg.de). This ensures that anyone who considers themselves or a (former) colleague deserving authorship can be identified and included. Potential additional authors need to contact the primary and senior authors to argue as to why they should be included. Should any conflicts arise, the manuscript’s submission will be paused to initiate the Ombudsman process for dispute resolution as described in the [Regulations of the University of Freiburg on Safeguarding Academic Integrity](#). Ombudsman of the respective institutions will be used to resolve disputes. If there is not one for a certain institute, the Ombudsman of the coordinating institute (ALU) will be approached.

3. Manuscript circulation. At least **one week before submitting a manuscript to a journal/book, the entire manuscript** must be emailed to all RestPoll members (restpoll@nature.uni-freiburg.de). Potential additional authors need to contact the primary and senior authors to argue as to why they should be included. Should any conflicts arise, the manuscript's submission will be paused to initiate the Ombudsman process for dispute resolution.

It is advised that manuscripts that are not directly within RestPoll, but used the same sites or Living Lab events, also circulate the abstract amongst the consortium following the above procedure.

6. Data management workflow

Data shall be **managed by the Task leaders** and stored at the partner organisations, and at a **joint drive** (Fig. 2) set up by UFR for data exchange within the project, following EU standards. All data gathering conforms to GDPR (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>) through its Data Protection Officer. No personal data shall be stored on the joint drive other than perhaps contact details of RestPoll members. Information on stakeholder such as farmers shall be anonymized before the upload of files to the joint drive.

Figure 2. Illustrative overview of the workflow for data management and publication of data and peer-reviewed studies.

We encourage storing data in **excel files** and **GeoPackages** (for spatial data). Excel files shall be organised according to the tidy data principles (<https://www.jstatsoft.org/article/view/v059i10>) and include a ReadMe tab containing metadata. Column names are aligned with the **RestPoll data dictionary**, an exhaustive list of all variables used, each listed once with its definition (metadata), to ensure quick comprehension and easy integration of different data sets.

We encourage **sharing R code** and other software code via the joint **RestPoll drive** and/or **GitHub**. A RestPoll group has been created on GitHub: <https://github.com/RestPoll>. Excel files are converted to **ODS files** (an open-source format) at the time of publication, which typically should be done when publishing a peer-reviewed study.

Qualitative data, such as transcription of interviews should be integrated into a word document. The document should include a summary at the beginning, which includes a list of WP(s) involved, a description of the interview, the dates and the objective. The document will be divided by title and subtitle. The title will describe the objective, the period and the interviewer. The subtitle will recall the codename of the interviewee and the date.

Publications shall be sent to Amibeth Thompson and Rachel Taylor (rachel.taylor@hvrgroup.nl) to be agreed on the content with Alexandra Klein and Elise Groot and then to be upload it to the RestPoll website. HVR may then initiate outreach activities to promote the publication. Please inform Amibeth and Rachel about publications or activities, so that press releases or advertisements can be created and disseminated in a timely manner.

WP7 has provided online training for data management in multi-actor projects including a detailed RestPoll data management plan, meta-data training following standards of ABCD (Access to Biological Collection data) and AgMES (Agricultural Metadata Element Set). Please see M27 for more details. The **data management plan** (D7.2) describes how files should be named and how excel files should be structured. **Protocols** shall specify what variables will be recorded; these typically include date of data collection (or action), site identity, observer(s), etc.

7. Open Science Policy

7.1. OPEN ACCESS REQUIREMENTS

Under Horizon Europe, the European Commission mandates that **all peer-reviewed publications** stemming from its project funding are **open access** (OA), meaning they are freely available online with no restrictions on use, by depositing them in a **trusted repository** by the **time of publication**, as embargoes are no longer permissible.

Open access to all peer-reviewed publications must be ensured, i.e.:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications (see below for more information);
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the **Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY)** or a licence with equivalent rights; more restrictive licensing that exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) are allowed for monographs and other long-text formats;
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

Authors must **retain intellectual property rights** to meet these open-access requirements, which is achieved by publishing under the above-mentioned licences.

Metadata should be in line with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. They should be machine-actionable (i.e. machine-readable, and automatic computer processing can extract information from the metadata attributes ensuring a cross-linking between different research outputs) and follow a standardised format. At least the following information should be provided: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant.

Only **publication fees in fully open-access journals** for peer-reviewed scientific publications are **eligible for reimbursement out of the grant**. Partners may **request ALU to cover these fees** using their **allocated grant funds**, for publications in OA journals during the project period that involve a considerable part of the consortium. For this ALU has to be invoiced by the journal for the publication fees in **agreement with Amibeth Thompson**.

For studies involving large parts of the consortium ALU can be asked to pay the publication fees out of their budget.

Publication fees in Hybrid Open Access journals are not eligible for reimbursement.

To help you find publishing venues that comply with Horizon Europe open access requirements, you can use:

- the [Journal Checker Tool](#) – can help to determine whether a specific publishing venue allows compliance with the open access obligations of Horizon Europe;
- the [Directory of Open Access Journals](#) – can help to identify full open access journals that allow open access publishing under CC BY or an equivalent licence;
- [Open Research Europe](#) – open access publishing platform of the European Commission, allows automatic compliance with the Horizon Europe requirements.

Even if you publish in a fully open-access journal, you **must upload your publication in a trusted repository**.

Trusted repositories are:

- Certified repositories or disciplinary and domain repositories commonly used and endorsed by research communities. Such repositories should be recognized internationally. Please see D7.2 Data management plan, section 9 for examples;
- General-purpose repositories or institutional repositories that present the essential characteristics of trusted repositories.

ResearchGate and Academia.edu are **NOT** considered such repositories.

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

The RestPoll case-study area and living lab network information and finalised protocols must be linked (via an API) to the [Oppla platform](#). [Entered for each case study area; more information to come]. We will use the Zenodo repository for making publications of peer-reviewed articles open access. A RestPoll community has been created for storing our publications: <https://zenodo.org/communities/restpoll>.

8. Additional open science guidelines

Beyond the mandatory open access rules, everyone is encouraged to follow the [Horizon Europe open science guidelines](#) that involve making data, knowledge and tools as openly available as possible but keeping them as closed as necessary. This could mean making curated scientific datasets publicly available on the [Zenodo repository](#) in reference to a licence (CC BY is recommended). The datasets should include metadata that describe e.g. in which context the data were collected and how the recorded parameters are defined.

Open and early engagement of various key knowledge contributors, such as academic institutions, industry, government bodies, land users, citizens, and the broader society is encouraged.

You must however ensure that personal and other sensitive information are protected as described in the grant agreement (particularly articles 13, 15 and 16).

9. Version 2

Feedback and comments from consortium members were implemented, including updated information. Section 2 (point 6), 3.3 and 3.4 were added.

10. Version 3

Section 2.2 Communication expectations was updated from feedback from consortium members regarding communication towards stakeholders at the CSA / LLs.

11. Version 4

“Multi-level coordination structure” (Section 2) was added. Section 3.1 Internal communication channels was updated and a division (3.2. Platforms with Project information) was added.

12. Appendices

10.1. APPENDIX 1

Deliverable and Milestone Template

RestPoll^L

Title of the deliverable

WPX: NAME OF WORKPACKAGE
TASK X.X: TITLE OF TASK

Deliverable Dx.y

DD Month YYYY

Author(s)
Author affiliations

RestPoll
Restoring Pollinator habitats across European agricultural landscapes based on multi-actor participatory approaches

2 Dx.y: Brief deliverable title

Prepared under contract from the European Commission
Grant agreement No. 101082102
EU Horizon Europe Framework Programme

Project acronym: **RestPoll**
Project full title: **Restoring Pollinator habitats across European agricultural landscapes based on multi-actor participatory approaches**

Start of the project: Oct 2023
Duration: 48 months
Project coordinator: Professor Alexandra-Maria Klein
University of Freiburg, Freiburg, Germany
www.restpoll.eu

Deliverable title: [AS REPORTED IN THE GA]
Deliverable n°: Dx.y
Nature of the deliverable: [Report, Prototype, Demonstrator, Other]
Dissemination level: [Public, Restricted, Confidential]

WP responsible: WPx
Lead beneficiary: [Organization]

Citation: Surname, I, Surname, I & Surname, I (YYYY). Deliverable title. Deliverable Dx.y EU Horizon RestPoll Project, Grant agreement No. 101082102.

Due date of deliverable: Month n°
Actual submission date: Month n°

Deliverable status:

Version	Status	Date	Author(s)
L0	Final/Draft	DD Month YYYY	Name Organization

The content of this deliverable does not necessarily reflect the official opinions of the European Commission or other institutions of the European Union.

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

3 Dx.y: Brief deliverable title

Table of contents

Preface4
Summary4
1. Heading level 14
 1.1. Heading level 24
 1.1.1. Heading level 34
2. Another heading level 14
 2.1. Another heading level 24
 2.1.1. Another heading level 34
3. Acknowledgements4
4. References4

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

4 Dx.y: Brief deliverable title

Preface

Main text (Lora point II; single line spacing; full justification; 1 line spacing between paragraphs; no other spacing before or after paragraphs)

Bullet lists:

-

Table 1: Table caption (above table).

Column heading1	Column heading2	Column heading3	Column heading4	Column heading5	Column heading6	Column heading7
Row label	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Row label	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Row label	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

Figure 1: Figure caption (below figure).

Refer to as Figure 1 and Table 1 within the main text.

1.1. SUMMARY

Short (maximum 1 page) executive summary of the deliverable

2. Heading level 1

2.1. HEADING LEVEL 2

2.1.1. HEADING LEVEL 3

Heading level 4

3. Another heading level 1

3.1. ANOTHER HEADING LEVEL 2

3.1.1. ANOTHER HEADING LEVEL 3

Another heading level 4

4. Acknowledgements

5. References

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under project No. 101082102.

10.2. APPENDIX 2

Financial risk mitigation process form

Task x.x: financial risk mitigation process

Identify and explain the problem, risk and impact, and the cost and timescales associated with risk

Problem:

Risk:

Impact:

Proposed mitigation

Cost:

Approximate timescales:

Demonstrate you have reviewed your budget to see where costs can be streamlined to make funds available.

Seek 'free of charge' resources both within organisation and within consortium.

Demonstrate that this has been considered

See where costs can be streamlined across your WP to make funds available (with WP leader).

Demonstrate that this has been considered